

Diagnostic tests are an integral part of infectious disease control strategies. Accurate diagnosis requires specific diagnostics tests, either detecting the pathogen itself or the host's pathogen-specific immune response. These diagnostic tests can be molecular (for the detection of genetic material, i.e. DNA/RNA), or immunoassays, mainly aimed to identify exposure (past or present) to a pathogen through the identification of pathogen's proteins (antigens) or the detection of pathogen-specific antibodies in biological samples like blood e.g., enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA) and lateral flow immunoassays (LFIA).

ELISA – Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay

Principle

This assay is performed using small plastic boxes containing small wells (96-wells microplates). The plastic of these microplates has enhanced binding capacity for biomolecules (antigens or antibodies).

Procedure (direct ELISA for detection of pathogen exposure)

1. Distribution of the samples containing the antigen into the wells of the microplate for binding and immobilization.
2. Addition of a colour-labelled antigen-specific detection antibody.
3. Colour measurement (quantitative result).

Strengths

- High sensitivity and specificity
- Quantitative results
- High reproducibility

Limitations

- Requires laboratory setting
- Longer turnaround time (1–4 h)
- Needs trained personnel
- Medium-high costs

LFIA – Lateral flow immunoassay

Principle

This rapid assay is performed using a small strip of porous paper on which appropriately labelled antigen-specific antibodies have been attached on transversal lines.

Procedure

1. The sample is applied at one end of the strip of paper and begins to migrate by capillary action.
2. If the antigen is present in the sample, it binds to the antibody, and a visible coloured line is formed.

Strengths

- Very fast (5–20 min)
- Portable, Point-of-Care (PoC)
- Extremely easy to use
- Low costs

Limitations

- Lower sensitivity compared to ELISA
- Mainly qualitative/semi-quantitative
- Sample matrix interference possible

REPRODIVAC AIMS

- Develop a suite of immunological diagnostic tests, including ELISA and point-of-care LFIA to identify animals infected with pathogens
- These new diagnostics will be further developed by industrial partners and made accessible to users